

THE CONCEPT OF HOUSING IN THE GLOBAL WORLD

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Abstract

One of the most significant places of any nation throughout history was housing, providing shelter, a place to rest, safety, and warming facilities for humanity. In other words, housing is an inseparable component of the human. The typology of housing through the life cycle of history is continuously changing. This change is directly connected to the development of technology, and any period's social, political, and cultural situation, which is illustrated in the form of architecture and reflects the identity. The main research question of this essay is, "How the housing concept has changed globally?". As a research method to clarify this question, first, a theoretical understanding of the housing definition and its relation with the global world is discussed. Significant housing of different periods, from historical eras to contemporary housing, and efforts for future houses have been analyzed. As a result, each era's housing concept and typology are in specific relation to each period's social, political, economic, and knowledge.

Keywords: Global Housing, Housing Concept, Dwelling, Globalization, Global Housing

1. Introduction

There is no standard definition for “Housing,” and only different explanations by researchers exist, for instance, “Housing” as a commodity (Smith, 1776), a tangible asset with potential return (Ricardo, 1817), a fixed asset regardless the housing is owned or rented (Jevons, 1871). However, “housing” and “dwelling” are nouns and verbs. Housing is a material or a good that can be manufactured and demolished, produced and consumed, perceived and experienced, and bought and sold (Ruonavaara H., 2018). The concepts “housing” and “house” are similar as Melnikas (1998) described it as a specific and relatively limited, physically, biologically, and socially close place where people and groups of people can live their biosocial life by receiving services, performing house chores and other biosocial activity (Henikane I., 2016).

Housing typology is directly related to the conditions of any period, history, political situation, technology, knowledge development, and social environment. According to Rappaport, identity is distinguishing and identifying an element from another. It is a feature of the environment that does not change in different conditions, such as shape, size, decoration, construction style, etc. (Torabi Z., Brahman S., 2013)

2. Globalization and Housing

The transformation of housing is globally reflected as a result of the population growth rate, social and, economic, political changes, and the development of technologies and knowledge (Remali et al., 2016). As Turner (1976) mentioned, vernacular housing was a direct reflection of local knowledge, building method, materials, and local environment, climate, and cultural situation of the period and place.

Therefore, housing diversity progress during history is presented as a result of community changes and significant environmental situations as two of the most critical housing factors. New construction methods, materials, and political intervention occurred in new development tendencies in the case of settlements. According to Owens (1992), historical settlement cases are valuable to study housing development, such as Roman settlements, which followed housing standards including size, layouts, and rigid infrastructure.

3. Pre-Historical Housing

Archeologists in the 1950s had standardized plans, the first classification of them done by Olivier Aurenche in 1981, in which significant classes reflected the unicellular round buildings, round buildings with internal partitions, and unicellular rectangular and multicellular rectangular structures.

Concerning Rapoport (1968), many sub-typologies can be derived from these classifications to recognize the materials, construction method, functions of spaces, and climate conditions considerations.

Typologies of Neolithic House : Beidha Level II (a-b), Beisamoun (c), CAin Ghazal (d-e), Jericho (f-h), and Yiftahel (i). (Banning, 2003)

3.1.Catalhoyuk, 7400 BCE

Catalhoyuk as a housing type was significant for its inhabitants, and they would gradually build and rebuild their houses, which were very important aspects of their life. Catalhoyuk houses were rectangular but different in size and shape, closely built together with no streets in between. The inhabitants used to climb a ladder and use a hole in the roof as an entrance, walls constructed of mud bricks. Catalhoyuk housing includes interior features such as painting on the wall as decoration, an oven below the stairs in each central room, raised platforms within the rooms used for sleeping and other domestic activities, and a place under these platforms to bury dead inhabitants.

Reconstruction of Catalhoyuk showing the importance of the roof spaces. Illustration by John Swogger.

A reconstruction showing the use of space and the layout of a typical house. Illustration by Kathryn Kikkackey.

3D model of the entranceway to a house, showing the position of the oven below the ladder. Model created by Grant Cox.

by John Swogger

by, Kathryn Kikkackey

3D Model by Grant Cox

(Source: <https://www.catalhoyuk.com/>)

3.2. Stilt house 1200 BC

The houses were raised on stilts on the surface of the soil or water, built primarily to protect against flooding, and shady space under the house was used for work or storage.

Yawngnwe City in the Inle Lake, Myanmar, (Source: [Link](#))

3.3. Yurts 800 BC

A round tent covered and insulated with skins or felt was traditionally used as a temporary dwelling in central Asia for thousands of years. Yurts are constructed from a flexible structure made from wood or bamboo for walls, a door frame, and sometimes a wheel.

A traditional Kyrgyz yurt, (Source: [Link](#))

3.4. Insula 500 BC

In Roman architecture, an Insula was recognized as an apartment or even a block of the city where ordinary lower and middle-class people lived. Usually, shops and businesses were placed on the ground floor of the Insula, and other above spaces were occupied for living.

An Insula Remaining near the Capitolium and the Insula dell'Ara Coeli in Rome, (Source: [Link](#))

4. Historical Housing

4.1. The Roman Villa 1st Century

By the first century BC, many architectural forms represented the classic villas and were used by wealthy Roman citizens. The villa complex includes three main parts:

The first part of the villa was similar to rich persons' houses in the city belonged to the wealthy family where the owner and their family lived and were similar to the wealthy person's houses in the city; the other one where the chef and enslaved people lived and a place for the farm's animals, and the possibility of other rooms such as the store, hospital, and even a prison. The last part of the villa, called "fracture," would be the storage rooms, the place where all products of the estate, such as wine, grain, and grapes, were stored and ready to transport.

An ancient roman villa, (Source: [Link](#))

4.2. Tulou 17th Century

Between the 12th and 20th centuries, Chinese rural dwellings were primarily constructed in a round or even sometimes rectangular, large, enclosed form with load-bearing walls as a stability system. These large complexes covered smaller interior buildings used for different functions, such as gathering halls, living, or containing space. The solid outer structure is constructed with structural elements, including a mixture of compact soil and stone, wood, bamboo, and other materials, to create a wall up to 1.8m thick and three to four floors height to accommodate about 800 people (Colafranceschi, Pallottino, Porretta, 2020).

Tianluokeng Tulou cluster, (Source: [Link](#))

5. Industrialization Period Housing

After an industrial period, housing construction evolved into a highly standardized construction due to modern urban planning. Housing in the early industrial period during the nineteenth century reflected the tendency of people to reside individually and privately in their homes. At this moment, the phenomenon “Garden City” and “Suburban Housing” formed. The idea of single-family houses in suburban areas, a green, non-crowded place far from the central part of the city, emerged as a mass housing project in New York, a new town constructed called Levittown by William Levitt (Larrabee, 1979; Gans, 1967). After the vast population growth after World War II, people did not find apartments as suitable places to live and raise their families.

Soon a new phenomenon was invented by William Levitt, the suburban. He produced mass building in potato farms outside of New York by timber framing structures constructed of components such as Wall panels, Gables, Roof Trusses, Air conditioners, and Kitchen and Bathroom units. By combining these components, the house manufacturer had a flexible system to construct various forms of houses.

5.1. Birmingham – Back-to-Back Apartments 1800 – 1880

During the industrial revolution, people migrated from the countryside to cities to find factory jobs. As an industrial city, Birmingham provided working-class housing by factory owners of back-to-back typology.

Back-to-back housings were two to three-story buildings with minimal interiors with rooms less than 15 sqm. Ground floor facilities include washroom, kitchen, and bedrooms on the first floor with no windows or openings, blind-backs, and only one façade. This typology led people to death because of the epidemics and fire accidents that happened several times in history.

Back to Back Houses to the Garden Cities of England, (Source: [Link](#))

5.2. The Haussmann Apartment 1852 - 1870

After the double population growth in the 19th century in Paris, Haussmann and Napoleon third rebuilt the infrastructure of Paris and created the Haussmann apartments with the central concept of making Paris a unified city with buildings with the same style, color, and height lined with trees with shops on the ground floor.

Several different classes of families used to accommodate in these apartments that were classified by the floors and elevations, including:

- 2nd floor with a big terrace for the wealthiest family
- 3rd and 4th floor for the middle class
- And 5th floor belongs to the lower-class inhabitants, and a smaller terrace was placed for aesthetic reasons only.

Maid's room belonged to servants with a small size and shared water room and direct access to the kitchen by a service staircase. The first floor was for noble people with the tallest height, while the upper floor was less expensive for middle-class people. Moreover, each apartment included a large antechamber leading into a corridor that serves various adjoining rooms such as the dining room, living room, bedroom, reception, and bathroom on the inner courtyard side.

The Haussmannien apartment plan and section, (Source: [Link](#))

5.3.Pratt-Igoe

Pruitt-Igoe as a direct constructional response to the urban population growth after WW2 in St. Louis, USA. It was constructed for people living in the slums of St. Louis that had no warm water or central heat to move to a new home “Pruitt-Igoe.” For this purpose, a few architects tried to create a modern utopian society by how humans could live, work and interact. Flat roofs, asymmetrical geometric, volume emphasis, modernist materials, open-plan interiors, structural innovations, and rejection of ornaments defined a modernist movement.

By reducing the construction cost in Pruitt-Igoe, many maintenance problems occurred because of the low quality of materials, such as breaking the handles and cabinets the second time of use or breaking the windows because of winds. Furthermore, it resulted in high maintenance costs that inhabitants could not afford. Then wealthy inhabitants left for the suburbs. The Pruitt-Igoe was occupied by very low-income inhabitants and became a center of crimes that, finally, the government decided to disappear.

Widely televised demolition of a Pruitt–Igoe building on April 21, 1972, (Source: [Link](#))

5.4. Modern House 20th century

A revolution in technology, engineering, and building materials, modernism or modern buildings, emerged in the final years of the 19th century to express a new style of architecture based upon unique and innovative construction technologies such as glass, steel, and reinforced concrete. Modernism also said the idea of functionalism, to have a building more functional with the embrace of minimalism and rejection of ornament. One of the most iconic modern architecture is Villa Savoy by Le Corbusier, Paris, 1931, designed as a family retreat for the Savoyes. Its design illustrates the five points of modern architecture expressed by Le Corbusier: open plan, the grid of reinforced concrete columns (pilotis), the horizontal windows, the roof garden, and the independent façade. However, according to faulty construction and design mishaps, many problems happened in a few years that the family suffered, such as roof leaks and a poor heating system. As the most remarkable problem, finally abandoned the villa, and now it is used as a museum and one of the public buildings.

Villa Savoye, (Source: [Link](#))

5.5. Public and Social Housing

Public housing is usually owned by a central or local government authority to provide affordable housing whose developments are classified as housing projects, social housing, g, and private housing.

After the massive population growth due to the industrialization revolution, more dwellings needed to be provided for the people, therefore, social housing was one of the classifications of public housing owned by a state or non-profit organization or both to provide affordable housing.

Public housing in Bishan, Singapore - Social housing in Eunápolis, Brazil., (Source: [Link](#))

5.6. Pre-Fabricated Housing 1920s

In the post-second world war in the united kingdom, pre-fabricated housing was outlined by the prime minister (Ministry of works) due to the high demand for accommodation.

Prefab units had been planned for a minimum area of 59 square meters and a maximum of 2.3 meters wide to allow for transportation by road. These prefab units were called “service units,” The back-to-back typology is used for its planning to put the kitchen and bathroom in the same place for water pipes, west pipes, and electrical distribution, providing an easy installation.

Prefabricated farm buildings, (Source: [Link](#))

6. 3D Printed 2015

The first residential building was constructed in 2015 in Russia with an area of 298 sq. meters, which was constructed from prefabricated walls (printed in the factory) and assembling the elements on the construction site. This technology works directly on the construction site instead of printing in another place and assembling.

First 3D-printed house, (Source: [Link](#))

7. Future Housing

There are numerous concepts of how housing in the future will be. Some are the development of previous typologies, and others are new approaches according to the development of technologies such as Artificial Intelligence.

7.1. The Mars house

“Marsha” is designed by an AI space factory. In contrast with previous houses on Mars, it includes rooms, baths, windows, and a futuristic shape that is constructed by 3D printing of Basalt composite as a material that is easily made on Mars and works as an effective protector against high-energy radiations. Because of this high energy radiation that is 500,000 times more than the energy a person receives when living on earth, some experts argue that it would be impossible to live on Mars without protection. So, they also have some concepts of living underground with inspiration from “nuclear fallout shelters” on earth.

Marsha, Architecture on Mars, (Source: [Link](#))

8. Conclusion

The evaluation of prehistoric, historic, industrialization period, contemporary times, and finally, concepts for future housings exhibited a high level of the relationships among housing typology and social, cultural, and technological development to configure spatial parameters. The first phase of the study, including prehistoric, historical, and industrialization case studies, reflects the evolution of housing to both cultural needs and various environmental conditions. With emerging the industrialization, buildings mostly followed the international spatial configurations and standards caused by the global economic force. Contemporary housing carries out new housing standards due to the local condition, population, and land value growth, such as social housing and small residential units. By exploring case studies, the housing typology change is noticeable. People used to take more prominent places to establish their houses, such as Roman Villa. Later, after the emergence of industrialization and the modern period, spaces and living area sizes were reduced to smaller units, from dense vernacular buildings to larger suburban houses and finally to dense social and public residential towers and blocks (Remali, Salama, Wiedmann, & Ibrahim, 2016).

Technology, construction methods, and knowledge were essential in housing typologies in all periods. Now, with emerge of 3d printing technology and the growth of knowledge of life outside of the earth, man is trying to transfer their habitant and establish a typology matching new conditions that man never experienced before. This effort is evident in the production of Marsha, a new housing typology on Mars.

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